

Original article

Prevalence of olfactory dysfunction among pregnant women attending the antenatal clinic at the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital (UMTH)- Implications on gravidity and parity.

Fatima S. Arfo,¹ Abubakar Adamu,¹ Hajja B. Shettima,¹ Bello B. Usman,¹ Suleiman I. Kayode,² Bukar Lawan,¹ Aliyu JD,² Abdulmajid I. Yahya,¹ Idris Ibrahim,¹ Adeniyi O. Gabriel,¹ Bashir I. Kanuriana,¹ Ibrahim H. Garandawa,¹ Mala B. Sandabe,¹ Aliyu M. Kodiya. ¹

¹Departments of Ear, Nose and Throat, Head and Neck Surgery, University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital, PMB 1414 Bama Road, Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria

²Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital

Corresponding Author: Dr Fatima Shettima Arfo, Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Head and Neck Surgery, University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital, Maiduguri, Borno State. Email: fatiarfo@yahoo.com Tel: 08030644174

Abstract

Background: Olfaction plays an essential role in human well-being and quality of life. During pregnancy, it contributes to maternal and fetal safety by helping detect potentially harmful substances. Changes in olfactory function, including impairment, have been frequently reported among pregnant women. **Objective:** This study aimed to determine the prevalence of olfactory dysfunction among pregnant women by utilising the Sniffin' Sticks test battery. **Materials and Methods:** A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at the antenatal clinic of the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital (UMTH). Ethical approval was secured from the institution's research ethics board. Participants completed a structured questionnaire, underwent ENT examinations, and olfactory function was evaluated using the Sniffin' Sticks test battery. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 25, with significance set at $p \leq 0.05$. **Results:** A total of 174 pregnant women and age-matched non-pregnant controls were assessed. Participants were aged 18–45 years, with a mean age of 27 ± 6.6 years for the cases and 26 ± 6.6 years for the controls. Hyposmia was more prevalent among pregnant women (12.6%) compared to controls (8%). Women pregnant for the first time exhibited better olfactory scores than those with multiple pregnancies, suggesting a decline in olfactory performance as the number of pregnancies increased. **Conclusion:** The majority of pregnant women had normal olfactory function; however, they were more likely to develop olfactory dysfunction. The subjective report of smell impairment was 25%, while objective testing revealed a prevalence of 12.6%. A decline in olfactory ability correlated with the number of prior pregnancies.

Keywords: Olfaction, Olfactory dysfunction, Pregnancy, Sniffin Sticks

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Introduction

Pregnancy is a natural physiological process marked by multiple systemic changes, including alterations in cardiovascular, respiratory, haematological, and renal systems, primarily driven by rising hormone levels.¹ The elevated sex hormones during pregnancy increase vascular flow to the nasal mucosa, which can result in congestion and swelling, thereby affecting the sense of smell.^{2,3} The sense of smell, or olfaction, is a vital sensory modality that enables individuals to recognize and distinguish various odors. It plays a crucial role in detecting hazardous substances, supporting adequate nutrition, influencing social interactions, and contributing to the enjoyment of food and the environment.⁴ Olfaction is essential for detecting dangerous compounds, maintaining nutrition,

interpersonal behaviour, and the sensation of pleasure.⁵

Many expectant mothers, particularly those in their first pregnancy (primigravidae), may experience either heightened olfactory sensitivity (hyperosmia) or a diminished ability to perceive odours (hyposmia).^{6,7} These fluctuations typically resolve or stabilize as gestation advances.^{6,7} In some cases, pregnant women report intolerance to certain smells, which can disrupt daily routines when compared to non-pregnant individuals.⁴

Olfactory changes seen can either be qualitative or quantitative disorders.^{7,8,9} Nwankwo *et al.* in University College Hospital, Ibadan, reported a 7.1% prevalence of hyposmia in pregnant women compared to 2.9% in non-pregnant women.⁴ Another study revealed that approximately 11.27% of pregnant participants experienced heightened olfactory sensitivity, with no such findings among the control group.⁹

Olfactory changes during pregnancy have been suggested as one of the contributors to nausea and vomiting.⁴ Although the aetiology of hyperemesis gravidarum remains unclear, increased olfactory sensitivity is considered a potential factor.⁴ Studies have observed that olfactory dysfunction occurs across all trimesters, though symptoms may be more pronounced in the first and third trimesters and least evident during the second.⁴

Given that olfaction aids in aroma detection and offers a protective mechanism against consuming harmful substances, any disturbance, such as that brought on by pregnancy, could affect taste and reduce appetite.¹⁰ Thus, understanding these olfactory changes is essential for providing appropriate counselling during prenatal care.

Aim of the Study:

This research was aimed at evaluating the prevalence of olfactory dysfunction among pregnant women attending antenatal care at the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital using the standardized Sniffin' Sticks test battery.

Materials and Methods

This investigation was designed as a cross-sectional, hospital-based study.

Ethical Considerations:

Approval for the study was granted by the hospital's Research and Ethics Committee (UMTH/REC/23/625). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants before their inclusion.

Study Population and Criteria:

The study enrolled 174 pregnant women using convenience sampling who had consented to

participate. Inclusion criteria required that participants be attending antenatal care at UMTH. Exclusion criteria comprised the presence of comorbidities such as diabetes mellitus, hypertension, or recent COVID-19 infection, as well as nasal disorders including congenital anosmia, allergic rhinitis, or a history of nasal surgery.

Data Collection Tools:

Data were gathered using a structured questionnaire that captured socio-demographic details (such as age, gestational age, occupation), clinical history (including nasal symptoms, previous nasal surgery, head trauma, and medication use), and self-reported smell disturbances.

Clinical Examination:

Each participant underwent a general ear, nose, and throat (ENT) examination, with a specific focus on the nasal cavity. This was done to rule out any structural abnormalities, such as nasal polyps, mucosal masses, or discharge, which could confound olfactory testing results.

Olfactory Assessment:

Olfactory function was objectively assessed using the *Sniffin' Sticks* test battery (Burghart Medical Technology, Wedel, Germany), which consists of three sub-tests:

- **Odour Threshold (OT) Test 11-15**
Participants were tested using a 3-alternative forced choice staircase method involving triplets of pens, only one of which contained n-butanol at ascending concentrations. Testing continued until the participant correctly identified the odoured pen twice in succession. Then, the concentration was decreased until an incorrect response was recorded. The final OT score was the average of the last four reversal points.
- **Odour Discrimination (OD) Test 11-15**
This test required participants to identify which of three pens (presented at 30-second intervals) had a different odour. The 16 triplets were arranged such that one pen (green cap) contained a unique odour, while the other two (blue and red caps) had identical ones. Participants were blindfolded to avoid visual cues. The maximum OD score was 16.
- **Odour Identification (OI) Test 11-15**
In this part, participants were shown one pen at a time (a total of 16 pens) and asked to select the corresponding odour from a list of four descriptors. The answers were aided by visual cues (words and pictures).

Each pen was presented only once, and 30 seconds were allowed between stimuli.

Scoring System¹¹⁻¹⁵

The total olfactory function was quantified using the composite Threshold, Discrimination, and Identification (TDI) score (maximum: 48). Classification was as follows:

- Anosmia: TDI score < 15.5
- Hyposmia: TDI score 16.5 – 30.5.
- Normosmia: TDI score > 30.5

Data Analysis:

All collected data were entered and analysed using SPSS version 25. The significance level was established at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results

The mean age of the participants in the study group (pregnant women) was 27 ± 6.6 years, while the control group (non-pregnant women) had a mean age of 26.2 ± 6.6 years. A summary of the socio-demographic variables is presented in **Table 1**. The majority of the pregnant participants were multigravidae and were primarily in their second trimester. A considerable proportion had between three to four previous pregnancies.

Table 1: Distribution by Socio-Demographic Variables

Variables	Control		Cases	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Age	26.2	6.6	27.0	6.6
Ethnicity	Number	%	Number	%
Kanuri	36	20.7	63	36.2
Babur/Bura	36	20.7	23	13.2
Shuwa	11	6.3	8	4.6
Others	94	54.0	80	46.0
Total	174	100	174	100
Marital Status				
Single	18	10.3	6	3.4
Married	152	87.4	167	96.0
Divorced	1	.6	0.0	0.0
Widowed	3	1.7	1	0.6
Total	174	100	174	100
Educational Status				
None	11	6.3	5	2.9
Primary	10	5.7	24	13.8
Secondary	84	48.3	67	38.5
Tertiary	69	39.7	78	44.8
Total	174	100	174	100
Occupation				
Unemployed	69	39.7	54	31.0
Student	34	19.5	43	24.7
Civil Servant	42	24.1	49	28.2
Self Employed	29	16.7	28	16.1
Total	174	100	174	100

Based on subjective assessment, 25% of pregnant women reported experiencing some alteration in their sense of smell during their pregnancy at the time of the study, whereas none of the non-pregnant controls reported such a change. Objective testing revealed that the majority of hyposmic cases occurred in the second trimester (79%), a difference that was statistically significant. Using the TDI score as a benchmark, the overall objective prevalence of olfactory dysfunction among the pregnant cohort was 12.6%, classifying them as hyposmic. **Figure 2** illustrates these findings.

Have you had abnormal smell during the current pregnancy?

Figure 1: Self-Reported Prevalence of Olfactory Dysfunction

Figure 2: Prevalence of Objective Olfactory Dysfunction Among Pregnant Women

- OI: Odor Identification
- OD: Odor Discrimination
- OT: Odor Threshold

• **TDI: Composite Score**
 Analysis comparing olfactory function between first-time pregnant women (primigravidae) and those with previous pregnancies (multigravidae) showed that primigravidae had significantly higher mean scores in odour identification (OI),

discrimination (OD), and the overall TDI score. Although the mean OT score was slightly better in multigravidae, the difference was not statistically significant.

Table 2: Olfactory dysfunction based on subjective assessment in cases.

Variables	Have you had abnormal smells during the past year?		χ ²	df	P-value	
	Yes	No				
Is this your First Pregnancy?	Yes	10	22	.522	1	0.470
	No	33	109			
	Total	43	131			
Trimester of Pregnancy	1 st Trimester	4	30	.645 ^a	2	0.724
	2 nd Trimester	8	75			
	3 rd Trimester	8	49			
	Total	20	154			
How is your sense of smell during the First Trimester?	Increased	24	12	64.096 ^a	2	0.000
	Decreased	10	7			
	Unchanged	9	112			
	Total	43	131			
How is your sense of smell during the Second trimester	Increased	4	3	5.962 ^a	2	0.051
	Decreased	4	7			
	Unchanged	24	93			
	Total	32	103			
How is your sense of smell during the Third Trimester	Increased	2	1	2.058 ^a	2	0.357
	Decreased	1	3			
	Unchanged	12	31			
	Total	15	35			

Table 3: Comparison of Olfactory Function Between Primigravidae and Multigravidae

Variables	Primigravida	Multigravida	Z-statistic	P-value
OI	11.70 ± 0.79	11.28 ± 0.91	7.042	0.009
OT	7.89 ± 0.52	8.00 ± 0.93	0.500	0.481
OD	10.85 ± 0.80	10.52 ± 0.87	4.494	0.035
TDI	30.44 ± 1.45	29.78 ± 1.54	5.745	0.018

P-value =0.05

Discussion

This study objectively assessed olfactory function among pregnant women attending antenatal care at the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital. The participants were aged between 18 and 45 years, with a mean of 27 ± 6.6 years; this is comparable to findings in previous studies conducted on women of reproductive age.^{9,16} For instance, Nwankwo et al. reported a mean age of

30.5 ± 3.9 years among women aged 22–38 years. The mean age of these women falls within the reproductive age group.² In this study, approximately 21% of participants experienced an increased sense of smell during the first trimester, a lower proportion than the 49% reported by Nwankwo et al.² Other studies have consistently observed heightened olfactory sensitivity in early pregnancy.^{17,18} Fessler *et al.* linked this phenomenon to increased disgust

sensitivity during early gestation, which is a period marked by immunosuppression¹⁹. Similarly, Nordin et al. observed a heightened response to aversive odours in pregnant women, which may serve a protective function for the developing fetus.²⁰

The increased smell sensitivity seen early in pregnancy may represent an elevated awareness or irritation caused by many odours, often referred to as olfactory hypersensitivity.⁷ This symptom is commonly reported in the first trimester. Mgbe et al. documented hyperosmia in 11% of their study,⁹. This is comparable to that of Onyeagwara et al. in Benin ²¹Although Kim et al. found increased subjective sensitivity among pregnant women, they observed no corresponding change in objective olfactory function.²²

The current study also observed a relatively high self-reported decline in smell perception (31%) during the first trimester, a figure consistent with literature indicating olfactory impairment is most common early in pregnancy and tends to improve as gestation progresses . ²These changes are likely driven by hormonal, vascular, and neurological shifts that accompany pregnancy. Some researchers suggest that increased levels of human chorionic gonadotropin and enhanced vascularization of the nasal mucosa may underlie these olfactory variations.⁷

With the objective assessment, a higher prevalence of hyposmia (12.6%) was found in the pregnant cohort compared to 8% among non-pregnant controls. Most hyposmic cases were observed during the second trimester, aligning with earlier findings by Nwankwo et al.,² who also identified the second trimester as a period with increased olfactory disturbances.⁴

While some authors have shown pregnant women perform better in odour identification tests, others have reported contrary results, showing either no difference or lower scores among pregnant women.^{8,24,29,30} This study found that primigravidae had significantly higher OI scores compared to multigravidae. These findings agree with those of Nwankwo et al. (² but contrast with studies that reported no significant difference in OI scores between pregnant and non-pregnant women.^{16,22,27,28} The OI score reflects higher-order cognitive functions involved in smell perception, including semantic memory and executive function.²³ Since pregnancy can impair cognitive abilities due to neurohormonal changes, the lower OI scores observed in multigravidae may be due to cumulative cognitive and sensory fatigue.²⁴⁻²⁶ Brain imaging studies have shown that pregnancy can

reduce grey matter volume in areas related to cognition and memory, which may indirectly affect olfactory performance.^{24,26}

Interestingly, this study found that primigravidae had significantly higher OI scores compared to multigravidae. These findings agree with those of Nwankwo et al. (² but contrast with studies that reported no significant difference in OI scores between pregnant and non-pregnant women.^{16,22,27,28} While some authors have shown pregnant women perform better in odour identification tests, others have reported contrary results, showing either no difference or lower scores among pregnant women ^{248,29,30}

The odour discrimination (OD) test reflects the brain's ability to distinguish between different smells and relies on short-term memory and decision-making.^{12,31,32} Although OD scores were higher among primigravidae in this study, the difference was not statistically significant. This trend agrees with earlier reports that found no substantial difference in OD performance across gravidity or pregnancy status ^{2,33}.

The odour threshold (OT), which measures the lowest concentration of a substance detectable by smell, is indicative of peripheral olfactory sensitivity. In this study, OT scores were slightly higher among multigravidae, but not significantly. Previous studies, such as those by Wohlgemuth et al., have shown that OT values can decline during the third trimester and postpartum periods, potentially suggesting a cumulative sensory fatigue with multiple pregnancies.³⁴

Some studies, including Laska et al., found no consistent changes in olfactory thresholds across trimesters, although thresholds in pregnant women were significantly altered compared to non-pregnant controls.⁸ Others, such as Ochsenbein-Köblle et al., demonstrated a decrease in OT throughout pregnancy, with lower thresholds recorded in the third trimester and postpartum period.³⁵

The composite TDI score, which encompasses OT, OD, and OI, offers a comprehensive measure of olfactory function.^{11,12,31,32} In this study, primigravidae had significantly higher TDI scores than multigravidae, suggesting a decline in olfactory function with increasing parity. This result supports previous findings^{4,35,36} but contrasts with Wohlgemuth et al., who reported no significant decline in smell function with multiple pregnancies.³⁴

It is important to recognize that while pregnancy is linked to changes in olfaction, these alterations are typically transient and not permanent.³⁴ Although

some studies observed strong associations between pregnancy and olfactory changes, others found no meaningful correlation.^{37,38} The variations in outcomes across studies may reflect methodological differences or individual physiological variability.³³

Conclusion

Pregnancy, though a normal physiological process, is often accompanied by various systemic and sensory changes, including those affecting olfactory function. This study found that 12.6% of pregnant women had objectively measurable olfactory dysfunction when assessed using the Sniffin' Sticks test battery. Furthermore, olfactory performance was observed to decline with increasing parity, as evidenced by lower scores in multigravidae compared to primigravidae. These findings highlight the need to consider olfactory disturbances as a possible sensory alteration during prenatal care and patient counselling.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

References

1. Soma-Pillay P, Nelson-Piercy C, Tolppanen H, Mebazaa A. Physiological changes in pregnancy. *Cardiovascular Journal of Africa*. 2016 May 18;27(2):89-94.
2. Nwankwo U, Fasunla A, Oladokun A, Nwaorgu O. Comparison between olfactory function of pregnant women and non-pregnant women in the reproductive age group in Ibadan, Nigeria. *Niger Journal of Clinical Practice*. 2017;20(5):610-5.
3. Giambanco L, Iannone V, Borriello M, Scibilia G, Scollo P. The way a nose could affect pregnancy: severe and recurrent epistaxis. *Pan African Medical Journal*. 2019 Sep 24; 34:1-4.
4. Dikici O, Bayar Muluk N, Şahin E, Altıntoprak N. Effects of pregnancy on olfaction. *ENT Update* 2017;7(2):104-7.
5. Yang, Jingpu; Pinto, Jayant M. (2016). The Epidemiology of Olfactory Disorders. *Current Otorhinolaryngology Reports*, 2016;4(2):130-141. doi:10.1007/s40136-016-0120-6
6. Gilbert AN, Wysocki CJ. Quantitative assessment of olfactory experience during pregnancy. *Psychosomatic Medicine*. 1991; 53:693-700.
7. Cameron EL. Pregnancy and olfaction: a review. *Frontiers in Psychology*. 2014;5(FEB):1-11.
8. Laska M, Koch B, Heid B, Hudson R. Failure to demonstrate systematic changes in olfactory perception in the course of pregnancy: A longitudinal study. *Chemical Senses*. 1996;21(5):567-71.
9. Mgbe RB, Umana AN, Adekanye AG, Offiong ME. Ear, nose, and throat changes observed in pregnancy in Calabar, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*. 2017 Nov 30;23(2):355
10. Nordin S. A Longitudinal Descriptive Study of Self-reported Abnormal Smell and Taste Perception in Pregnant Women. *Chemical Senses*. 2004 Jun 1;29(5):391-402.
11. Hummel T, Sekinger B, Wolf SR, Pauli E, Kobal G. 'Sniffin' Sticks': Olfactory Performance Assessed by the Combined Testing of Odour Identification, Odor Discrimination and Olfactory Threshold. *Chemical Senses*. 1997;22(1):39-52.
12. Rumeau C, Nguyen DT, Jankowski R. How to assess olfactory performance with the Sniffin' Sticks test ®. *European Annals of Otorhinolaryngology, Head Neck Diseases*. 2016 Jun;133(3):203-6.
13. Lotsch J, Reichmann H, Hummel T. Different Odor Tests Contribute Differently to the Evaluation of Olfactory Loss. *Chemical Senses*. 2008 Jan 1;33(1):17-21.
14. Haehner A, Mayer A-M, Landis BN, Pournaras I, Lill K, Gudziol V, et al. High Test-Retest Reliability of the Extended Version of the "Sniffin' Sticks" Test." *Chemical Senses*. 2009 Oct 1;34(8):705-11.
15. Shu C-H, Yuan B-C, Lin S-H, Lin C-Z. Cross-Cultural Application of the "Sniffin' Sticks" Odor Identification Test. *American Journal of Rhinology & Allergy*. 2007 Sep 9;21(5):570-3.
16. Nordin S, Broman DA, Bringlöv E, Wulff M. Intolerance to ambient odors at an early stage of pregnancy. *Scandinavian Journal of Psychology*, 2007, 48, 339-343
17. Kershaw JC, Mattes RD. Nutrition and taste, and smell dysfunction. *World Journal of Otorhinolaryngology - Head Neck Surgery*. 2018;4(1):3-10.
18. Pence TS, Reiter ER, DiNardo LJ, Costanzo RM. Risk factors for hazardous events in olfactory-impaired patients. *JAMA*

- Otolaryngology - Head Neck Surgery*. 2014;140(10):951-5.
19. Fessler DMT, Eng SJ, Navarrete CD. Elevated disgust in the first trimester of pregnancy: Evidence supporting the compensatory prophylaxis hypothesis. *Evolution and Human Behaviour Journal*. 2005; 26:344-3
 20. Nordin S, Broman DA, Wulff M. 2005. Environmental odor intolerance in pregnant women. *Physiology and Behavior Journal*. 2005; 84:175-179
 21. Onyeagwara NC, Paul BO, Adam VY. Otorhinolaryngological manifestations in pregnant women in a tertiary hospital in South-South, Nigeria. *Niger Journal of Otorhinolaryngology*. 2018; 15:29-35.
 22. Kim HJ, Park HJ, Park JY, Park HE, Lee SS, Bae JH. The Possibility of Morning Sickness from Olfactory Hypersensitivity during Pregnancy. *Korean Journal of Otorhinolaryngology Head and Neck Surgery*. 2011;54(7):473.
 23. Hedner M, Larsson M, Arnold N, Zucco GM, Hummel T. Cognitive factors in odor detection, odor discrimination, and odor identification tasks. *Journal of Clinical Experimental Neuropsychology*. 2010; 32:1062- 1067.
 24. Hoekzema E, Barba-Müller E, Pozzobon C, Picado M, Lucco F, García D et al. Pregnancy leads to long-lasting changes in human brain structure. *Nature Neuroscience*. 2017; 20:287-296.
 25. Barth C, de Lange AMG. Towards an understanding of women's brain aging: the immunology of pregnancy and menopause. *Frontiers in Neuroendocrinology* 2020; 58:100850.
 26. Rehbein E, Kogler L, Kotikalapudi R, Sattler A, Krylova M, Kagan KO et al. Pregnancy, and brain architecture: associations with hormones, cognition, and affect. *Journal of Neuroendocrinology*. 2022;34: e13066.
 27. Buschhüter D, Smitka M, Puschmann S, Gerber JC, Witt M, Abol maali ND, Hummel T. Correlation between olfactory bulb volume and olfactory function. *Neuroimage Journal* 2008;42(2):498-502
 28. Simsek G, Bayar Muluk N, Arikan OK, Ozcan Dag Z, Simsek Y, Dag E. Marked changes in olfactory perception during early pregnancy: A prospective case-control study. *European Archives of Otorhinolaryngology* 2015; 272:627-30.
 29. Ochsenbein-Kolble N, von Mering R, Zimmerman R, Hummel T. Changes in olfactory function in pregnancy and postpartum. *International Journal of Gynaecology & Obstetrics* 2007; 97:10-4
 30. Mullol J, Alobid I, Mariño-Sánchez F, Quintó L, De Haro J, Bernal-Sprekelsen M, et al. Furthering the understanding of olfaction, prevalence of loss of smell and risk factors: A population-based survey (OLFACAT study). *BMJ Open*. 2012;2(6).
 31. Neumann C, Tsioulos K, Merkonidis C, Salam M, Clark A, Philpott C. Validation study of the "Sniffin' Sticks" olfactory test in a British population: a preliminary communication. *Clinical Otolaryngology*. 2012;37(1):23-7.
 32. Su B, Bleier B, Wei Y, Wu D. Clinical Implications of Psychophysical Olfactory Testing: Assessment, Diagnosis, and Treatment Outcome. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*. 2021; 15:1-12.
 33. Hummel T, Von Mering R, Huch R, Kölblle N. Olfactory modulation of nausea during early pregnancy? *BJOG An International Journal of Obstetrics & Gynaecology*. 2002;109(12):1394-7.
 34. Wohlgemuth C, Beinder E, Ochsenbein-Kölble N, Hummel T. Changes in olfactory function with several pregnancies? *Swiss Medical Weekly* 2008; 138:466-9.
 35. Cameron EL. Measures of human olfactory perception during pregnancy. *Chemical Senses* 2007; 32:775-82.
 36. Croy I, Landis BN, Meusel T, Seo HS, Krone F, Hummel T. Patient adjustment to reduced olfactory function. *Archives of Otolaryngology Head & Neck Surgery* 2011; 137:377-82.
 37. Festin M. Nausea and vomiting in early pregnancy. *Am Fam Physician* 2015; 92:516-7?
 38. Hummel T, Barz S, Pauli E, Kobal G. Chemosensory event-related potentials change with age. *Electroencephalography and Clinical Neurophysiology* 1998; 108:208-17.